

Roadmap for Decarbonisation of Cities

Cities have emerged as pivotal in the fight against climate change. As the world's population concentrates in urban areas, the environmental impact of cities has become increasingly evident. The urgent need to decarbonise urban spaces and transition towards sustainable, low-carbon alternatives has taken centre stage on the global agenda, particularly in the EU where urbanisation is highly prevalent.

This roadmap outlines a comprehensive strategy for the decarbonisation of cities, providing guidance for governments, city planners, policymakers, and stakeholders. By addressing key aspects of urban development and infrastructure, this roadmap seeks to achieve ambitious emission reduction targets while fostering resilient, livable, and environmentally conscious cities. The framework is adaptable to local circumstances, challenges, and opportunities, providing flexible pathways for implementation.

The roadmap focuses on three main implementation paths:

- 1. Sustainable energy transformation of the building stock.**
- 2. Development of a sustainable transportation system.**
- 3. Circular economy and sustainable consumption.**

Successful implementation requires collaboration among governments, businesses, civil society, and citizens. It calls for innovative financing mechanisms, effective governance, and active community engagement.

Key Messages

- 1. Urban areas are crucial in the fight against climate change due to their dense populations and significant environmental impact. As hubs of human activity, cities have the potential to drive transformative solutions for a sustainable future.**
- 2. Decarbonisation priorities focus on three key areas: transforming the building stock to improve energy efficiency and adopt renewable energy sources; developing sustainable transportation systems by prioritising electrification and active mobility options; and integrating circular economy practices to enhance resource efficiency and reduce waste.**
- 3. Enabling success requires collaborative strategies that engage governments, businesses, civil society, and citizens. Innovative financing**

mechanisms, such as green mortgages and public-private partnerships, are vital to accelerate progress. Leadership through pilot projects and the demonstration of best practices can inspire replication and foster widespread adoption of decarbonisation initiatives.

2. Lessons from successful case studies provide valuable insights for municipalities and project owners. Examples include Freiburg, Germany, a pioneer in solar energy and zero-energy buildings; Oslo, Norway, a global leader in electric vehicle adoption and zero-emission public transportation; Brussels, Belgium, which champions the circular economy through its "Be Circular" programme; and London, UK, which showcases the potential of retrofits through the Green Homes Grant initiative. Learning from these approaches can help cities identify effective strategies tailored to their local contexts.

3. Decarbonisation requires innovative solutions, active citizen engagement, and flexible strategies that adapt to the unique challenges and opportunities of each urban environment.

Building Sector Roadmap

The transformation of the building sector is critical for urban decarbonisation. The following six strategies provide a foundation for this transformation:

Mitigating greenhouse gas emissions

- Transition energy generation in buildings to renewable sources such as solar, wind, and geothermal energy.
- Implement district heating systems using renewable energy, coupled with thermal energy storage to manage demand fluctuations.

Reduced dependency on fossil fuels

- Encourage decentralised renewable energy generation to enhance energy security and reduce reliance on volatile fossil fuel imports.

- Strengthen local grids and incentivise rooftop solar installations through regulatory support.

Energy efficiency and demand reduction

- Retrofit buildings with insulation, energy-efficient windows, and high-efficiency HVAC systems.
- Promote smart building technologies for real-time energy monitoring and optimisation.

Cost savings and economic benefits

- Implement economic strategies like green mortgages and on-bill financing to finance retrofits and renewable energy installations.
- Highlight the non-energy benefits of retrofits, such as increased property value and improved occupant comfort.

Improved Indoor and Outdoor Air Quality

- Replace fossil-fuel-based heating systems with clean alternatives to reduce emissions of particulate matter and nitrogen oxides.

Demonstrating Leadership

- Showcase successful retrofits and renewable energy integration projects to inspire replication across regions.

Freiburg, Germany

Known as the "Green City," Freiburg has established itself as a pioneer in environmental sustainability. The city boasts an extensive solar district heating network that serves over 9,000 buildings, underscoring its commitment to renewable energy. Proudly self-described as Germany's environmental capital, Freiburg actively promotes the adoption of solar energy. Notable achievements include its innovative new city hall, one of the first zero-energy buildings in the world, featuring 800 solar panels integrated into its façade.

Additionally, the city's new soccer stadium showcases a cutting-edge solar installation on its roof, further solidifying Freiburg's reputation as a global leader in sustainable development.

[!\[\]\(0d5ec72f61334709c3fc9450209b754f_img.jpg\) Read more](#)

Transportation sector roadmap

The transportation sector is another cornerstone of urban decarbonisation. Strategies include:

Reduction of transportation emissions

- Electrify public transit and adopt renewable energy-powered vehicles, including hydrogen buses and biofuel-based fleets.

Decreased dependency on fossil fuels

- Expand EV charging infrastructure and integrate renewable energy into the grid.

Oslo, Norway

Oslo made history as the first city in the world to introduce its own Climate Budget. With significant investments in public transportation and bicycle infrastructure, the city has positioned itself as a global leader in sustainability

Improved air quality and public health

- Encourage active transportation modes, such as cycling and walking, supported by dedicated infrastructure.

Enhanced energy efficiency

- Develop integrated public transit systems to reduce reliance on private vehicles and optimise urban mobility.

Leadership and behavioural change

- Implement car-free zones and low-emission areas to promote sustainable practices.

and electric vehicle (EV) adoption. To boost EV sales, the Norwegian government introduced financial incentives, primarily in the form of generous tax cuts.

These efforts paid off: in 2020, 54% of the 141,000 newly registered passenger cars were fully electric (Statistisk sentralbyrå). Oslo has also electrified nearly all of its public buses, which now run on renewable energy sources such as biogas and electricity. Additionally, the city has created car-free zones in the city center and continues to promote EV adoption through a variety of supportive measures.

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Energy system integration roadmap

Effective energy system integration enhances sustainability by optimising resource use across sectors. Strategies include:

Optimal resource allocation

- Use smart grids and AI-based demand-response systems to balance energy loads.

Flexibility and resilience

- Couple renewable energy generation with battery storage to manage variability.

Demand-side management

- Implement peak shaving and load shifting using smart appliances and time-of-use pricing models.

Decentralisation and local energy systems

- Foster community energy projects and microgrids to reduce transmission losses and enhance resilience.

Technological innovation

- Pair renewable energy sources with emerging technologies like vehicle-to-grid (V2G) systems for energy sharing.

Circular economy and financing mechanisms

The adoption of circular economy practices, such as recycling materials, along with effective economic enabler strategies, plays a vital role in advancing renewable energy solutions in urban areas. These approaches promote resource efficiency and help attract private investment, foster innovative financing mechanisms, and make sustainable technologies more accessible and affordable to a broader range of stakeholders. Key strategies include:

- **On-bill financing:** Allow households to pay for renewable energy installations and retrofits through their utility bills.
- **Green mortgages:** Offer reduced interest rates for investments in energy-efficient buildings.
- **Public-private partnerships (PPPs):** Foster collaboration between local governments, private investors, and communities.

Brussels, Belgium

Brussels has introduced the "Be Circular" program to encourage the adoption of circular economy principles among existing businesses. This ambitious initiative aims to provide in-person training for 2,000 economic operators and reach an additional 20,000 through online resources.

The program spans 15 government administrative departments and engages over 60 stakeholder organisations from public, private, and academic sectors, fostering broad collaboration.

Key features of the "Be Circular" program include:

- Allocating €13 million annually to support circular economy initiatives.
- Offering grants for circular business projects and loans to promote sustainable practices across various sectors.

This comprehensive approach demonstrates Brussels' commitment to embedding circularity into its economic framework.

[← Read more](#)

London, United Kingdom

The Green Homes Grant Voucher Scheme (GHGVS), launched by the UK government, aimed to enhance energy efficiency in homes by offering financial incentives for home improvements. Homeowners could apply for vouchers covering up to two-thirds of the cost of energy-efficient measures, with a maximum value of £5,000—or £10,000 for low-income households.

The scheme garnered significant interest, receiving 169,430 applications for vouchers to improve 113,736 properties. By December 2021, 83,150 vouchers were issued,

resulting in 49,002 installations. While the initiative successfully stimulated consumer interest in energy-efficient upgrades, challenges emerged in matching demand with supply. Many applicants faced difficulties in finding certified installers to complete the work.

Despite these setbacks, qualitative feedback highlighted that the scheme motivated households to undertake energy-efficient installations they might not have otherwise considered, marking a step forward in promoting sustainable home improvements.

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Strategies for behavioural and cultural shifts

To achieve meaningful decarbonisation, behavioural and cultural shifts are as critical as technological advancements. Some of the strategies include:

Community education and awareness

- Launch public campaigns highlighting the benefits of decarbonisation initiatives, such as improved air quality and energy savings.

- Partner with schools and local organisations to integrate climate education into curriculums.

Incentivising sustainable choices

- Provide financial incentives for adopting energy-efficient appliances, EVs, and solar installations.

Participatory urban planning

- Engage citizens in co-creating sustainable urban spaces through workshops and public consultations.

Celebrating success and role models

- Recognise individuals, businesses, and communities excelling in sustainability practices through awards and public acknowledgment.
- Share success stories to inspire wider adoption of decarbonisation practices.

Addressing cultural barriers

- Tailor programs to local cultural contexts, ensuring inclusivity and equity.
- Conduct surveys and focus groups to identify and address resistance to change.

 [Read the full version of the RES4CITY Roadmap for Decarbonisation of Cities.](#)

www.res4city.eu

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#	RES Technology & RF Strategy in Urban Environment	TRL	Type	Technical Feasibility	Economic Feasibility	Circularity	Environmental Impact	Social Acceptance	Gender Issues
1	Solar PV	9	RES T	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Consolidated Technology - Easily Integration in urban context - No relevant maintenance 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Attractive LCOE - Grid Parity reached or close to be reached - Well established supply chain 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Possibility to sell on secondary markets (e.g., spare parts) - High quality recycled materials to feed PV module production process - Low quality recycled materials downcycled in processes with less stringent standard 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Land utilization - Visual impact - Utilization of hazardous materials - Mining of critical raw materials 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - General positive consensus for local installation - Possible opposition to large ground installation 	N.A.
2	Thermal Solar	9	RES T	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Well established technology - Easy integration in urban context - Relevant for buildings refurbishment 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Pay-back period between 3-5 years depending on the location - Attractive LCOH - Well established supply chain 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Recycled material used for their manufacturing - 90% of glass, polyurethane, and steel components to be collected and recycled 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Hazardous and chemical materials impact during the manufacturing process 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Positive consensus for small domestic installation - Possible opposition for large scale high temperature plants 	N.A.
3	Wind OnShore	9	RES T	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Difficult to consider in urban context (possibilities available in industrial areas) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Attractive LCOE - Grid Parity reached or close to be reached - Well established supply chain 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Re-utilization of blades in cement co-processing - Repurposing by using blades as furniture in the 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Visual Impact - Noise - Bird strikes - Lubricants leakage 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - High support to wind energy as a technology - Declining acceptance of 	N.A.

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				<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Existing examples of integration in buildings for small horizontal turbines - Developments in the field of vertical axial turbines 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - urban environment (e.g., playground, bikes shelters, etc.) - Recycling and recovery for producing fibers to reinforce concrete, to re-use the composite material for producing new objects, etc. 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - local wind projects 	
?4	Wind OffShore	9	REST	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Possible application in cities with adequate coastal conditions - Possible issues in cities with large port facilities - Specific climatic conditions required 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Attractive LCOE - Grid Parity reached or close to be reached - Well established supply chain 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Re-utilization of blades in cement co-processing - Repurposing by using blades as furniture in the urban environment (e.g., playground, bikes shelters, etc.) - Recycling and recovery for producing fibers to reinforce concrete, to re-use the composite material for producing new objects, etc. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Bird life (e.g., affecting migration routes) - Marine mammals (e.g., affecting movements and migration) - Ecosystem structure, functions, and processes (e.g., physical, hydrogeological, and physical characteristics) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - High support to wind energy as a technology - Ownership changes the acceptance level (e.g., local cooperative vs. large corporations) - If far from the coastline, higher acceptance 	N.A.
5	Geothermal	8-9	REST	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - High temperature geothermal possible only in specific locations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Geothermal energy at 90-150 °C competitive with 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Hybridization with other RES to reduce the need for geothermal 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Possible hydraulic and thermal changes in the deep underground 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Controversial cases available in the literature 	N.A.

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				<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Low temperature geothermal convenient in cities with Low external temperature - Possible issues connected with local geo-morphological conditions of the soil 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - respect to natural gas - Direct electricity production not competitive - High initial capital cost for low temperature geothermal coupled with heat pumps 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Reuse of some components (e.g., heat exchangers, pumps, etc.) for other applications - Repurposing abandoned coal mines or oil&gas wells for geothermal applications 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Geological interaction 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Acceptance limited by doubts linked to the security 	
6	Tidal	6-8	REST	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Exploitable only in specific locations - Scale between 0.1 and 2 MW - Predictable energy supply with possible applications in grid balancing 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Reliable supply chain to be developed - LCOE in 2030 is estimated in about 100 €/MWh - Economic feasibility achievable in the long period 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Technology is not mature enough for the elaboration of specific circular strategies. Anyhow the typical Reuse, Repurpose and Recycling approaches can be considered. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Habitat loss - Animal-infrastructure interaction - Location specific issues 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - General support towards the technology - Positive attitude to local project development 	N.A.
7	Wave	7-8	REST	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Specific wave conditions necessary - Only experimental prototypes available - Adequate for Oceanic coasts 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Reliable supply chain to be developed - LCOE in 2030 is estimated in about 150 €/MWh - Economic feasibility achievable in the long period 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Technology is not enough developed for the elaboration of specific circular strategies. Anyhow the typical Reuse, Repurpose and Recycling approaches can be considered. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Habitat loss - Animal-infrastructure interaction - Location specific issues 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - General support towards the technology - Positive attitude to local project development 	N.A.

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8	Solar CSP	7-8	RES T	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Useful for industrial areas with medium temperature processes - Possible combination with absorption heat pumps - Possible integration in urban context 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Less competitive with respect to PV and wind for electricity generation - LCOE around 200 €/MWh depending on the location - CAPEX reduction opportunities from learning curve development 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Possibility to sell on secondary markets (e.g., spare parts) - High quality recycled materials to feed PV module production process - Low quality recycled materials downcycled in processes with less stringent standard 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Land occupation - Water consumption - Leakage of thermal fluids 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Limited information available - A few studies in Morocco show a support towards large scale CSP projects 	N.A.
9	Fuell Cells	6-7	RES Technology	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Support the decarbonization of transport sector (e.g., heavy duty vehicles) - Necessity of a distribution infrastructure of hydrogen to support their diffusion - Existing technical and safety issues 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - High CAPEX in short medium term - Technology at very early market stage 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Recovering of non-critically damaged Fuel Cells - Disassembly of non-recoverable Fuel Cells and selection of components for direct re-use on secondary markets - Waste management for the non-recoverable parts through mechanical and chemical treatments to recover valuable material 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Difficulties in obtaining green hydrogen - High Environmental impact in the manufacturing phase, especially the electrocatalyst production - Utilization of critical raw material such as nickel, platinum, etc. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Safety concerns especially in mobility applications 	N.A.

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10	Solar PV/T	8-9	RES Technology	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - High level of integration in urban contexts - Maximization of the efficiency in relation to the occupied surface - Easy installation and maintenance 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Attractive LCOE/LCOH - Short pay-back period - Well established supply chain 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Possibility to sell on secondary markets (e.g., spare parts) - High quality recycled materials to feed PV module production process - 90% of glass, polyurethane, and steel components to be collected and recycled 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Visual impact - Hazardous and chemical materials impact during the manufacturing process 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Positive consensus for small domestic installation 	N.A.
11	Biomass	9	Renewable Fuel Technology	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Availability of local sources - Monitoring of soot emissions - Energy-Food Nexus 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Attractive economics if resources are locally available - Supply chain must be reliable - Possibility to develop local economy 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Possibility to integrate with wood industry - Utilization of wood waste to produce pellets 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Trade-off between land for food or biomass in case of dedicated cultivation - Soot emissions can be a problem - Ash management can be problematic in case of massive use 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Controversial attitude on local projects - Fear to sustain negative externalities 	N.A.
12	Biogas	9	Renewable Fuel Technology	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Potential availability in urban environment through anaerobic digestion of organic fraction of municipal waste - Well established production process 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Economically viable since it is primary conceived for waste treatment - Stable supply chain - Possible synergies between urban and rural areas if 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Integration between waste management and energy generation - Value extraction from farming organic waste - Opportunities related to the 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Possibility of biogas leakage - Imperfect production could lead to more emissions than expected 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Controversial attitude on local projects - Fear to sustain negative externalities 	N.A.

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				- Synergic approach with municipal waste management services	biogas from farming is considered	production of char (fertiliser) for agriculture			
13	Hydrogen	7-8	Renewable Fuel Technology	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Renewable fuel for decarbonizing complex sectors (e.g., high temperature heat demand) - Technical complexities related to its distribution and storage - Potential large availability irrespectively from the location 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - High investment costs - Supply chain to be built - Uncertain business model 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Recycled water from other processes can be used as input in the hydrogen production 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Low or close to zero environmental impact if produced via electrolysis and RES 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Positive attitude toward the technology - Decreasing level of support for infrastructure development 	N.A.
14	Syngas	8-9	Renewable Fuel Technology	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Established technology, can be used for both electricity and thermal energy production - It requires wood feedstock (low moisture content) - Low TRL syngas technologies are being developed for expanding the usable feedstock 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - High investment costs - To guarantee a reliable supply chain for the operation - Uncertain business model 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Circularity opportunities related to the production of char (fertiliser) for agriculture 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Closely linked to the biomass used in the process 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Difficult to assess due to the limited impact and small nature of these plants 	N.A.

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				- It needs to be used locally (injection of biogas in natural gas pipelines not possible)					
15	Liquid Biofuels	8-9	Renewable Fuel Technology	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Availability of local sources, e.g., local exhausted vegetable oils - Blending with other liquid fuels - Energy-Food Nexus 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Attractive economics if resources are locally available - Supply chain must be reliable - Possibility to develop local economy 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Possibility to integrate with waste treatment industry (i.e., organic waste) and food industry - Recycling of exhausted vegetable oils 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Trade-off between land for food or biofuel in case of dedicated cultivation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Controversial attitude on local projects - Fear to sustain negative externalities 	N.A.
16	Heat Pumps	7-9	Technology	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Coupling of electricity and thermal sectors - Consolidated technology - Possibility to couple with many different RES 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Market growing at a high pace - CAPEX of 600 €/kW - Well established supply chain and developed EU industrial system 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Recycling of metal materials - Re-utilization of refrigerants - Modular design and better reparability as drivers for improving circularity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Approximately equal to traditional system - Possible reduction of NOx emissions - Toxicity of refrigerants can be an issue 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Visual impact and space requirements as possible barriers for acceptance - Premium property value as a driver to overcome acceptance issues 	N.A.
17	Green Roofs/Green Walls	8-9	Technology	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Positive integration with urban environment - Not complicated to implement 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - CAPEX of around 100 €/m² - Substantial non-energy benefits 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Higher lifecycle of green roofs/walls protects the supporting infrastructure 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Positive environmental impact - Reduction of urban heat island 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Positive consensus for local projects 	N.A.

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				<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Beneficial micro-climatic impact - Lack of common standards 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Established supply chain 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - determining less replacement - Gray water recovery - Easy management of the components at end of life 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Reduction of water run-off from buildings - Reduction of carbon emissions 		
18	Special Glazing	9	Technology	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Easy to apply - Very large potential - Passive method to reduce energy consumption 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Viable solutions available on the market 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Recycling cycle to be implemented at the end of life 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Reduced energy consumption for air conditioning 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Positive consensus for local projects 	N.A.
19	Building Facade	9	Technology	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Passive method to reduce energy consumption - Easy to implement - Extensive impact 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Viable solutions available on the market 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Recycling cycle to be implemented at the end of life 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Reduced energy consumption for air conditioning/heating - Better ventilation opportunities 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Positive consensus local projects 	N.A.
20	ORC	8-9	Technology	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Recovering of low temperature energy sources for electricity production - Well developed technology for medium/large system sizes - Low conversion efficiency 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - High investment costs which make small-size systems not economically feasible 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Recycling of metal materials - Utilization of spare parts on secondary markets - Modular design and better repairability as drivers for improving circularity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - It depends on the fluids used in the cycle - Sustainable fluids are constantly under development 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Difficult to assess due to the limited impact and small nature of these plants 	N.A.
21	Thermal Storage	7-9	Technology	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Decoupling of thermal energy production and consumption 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Quick pay-back period for small systems for 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Recycling of metal materials 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Very low for domestic water-based systems 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - High level of support for domestic system 	N.A.

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				<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Integration with other technologies (e.g., solar thermal, heat pumps, etc.) - Scalable solutions available 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - domestic application - High level of uncertainties for large systems 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Utilization of spare parts on secondary markets - Modular design and better repairability as drivers for improving circularity in large systems 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Linked to the accumulation medium for large systems 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Decreasing support for large installations as for all the technologies 	
22	Phase Change Materials	6-8	Technology	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Option to increase the performance of thermal storage systems - Most of them derived from hydrocarbons, some bio-based solutions available - Easy applicable 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Low installation cost during the construction phase - Very variable CAPEX depending on the type of PCM 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Recycling at the end of life - Different strategies depending on PCM typologies - Possible symbiosis with organic waste treatment 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Low impact for PCM deriving from food waste 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - No substantial data available for a comprehensive evaluation 	N.A.
23	Energy Excess recovery	N.A.	Technology	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Possible integration with existing DH network - Combination with absorption heat pumps - Energy recovery through ORC 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - It can be very convenient depending on the temperature level of the source - Possibility for industrial symbiosis 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Example of circularity since waste heat is used to feed another process - Steel used for the infrastructures (e.g., pipes) can be recycled at the end of life 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Usually very limited since it is implemented in industrial areas - Often it implies only the installations of heat exchangers and pipes 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Closely linked to the infrastructure to build 	N.A.

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24	Low Temperature DH	8-9	Technology	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Integration with high available low temperature energy sources - Reduction of energy losses - Possibility to develop 100% RES systems 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Profitability depending on the location of installation - Possibility to retrofit existing high temperature network - Competitiveness of the possible tariffs depending on fossil fuel market 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Linked to the different technologies integrated in the community 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Reduction of fossil fuel consumption - Reduction of wasted energy - Resource optimization 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Overall high acceptance - If it is a retrofit, strong support is expected - Possible opposition in case of a new infrastructure development 	N.A.
25	Absorption Heat Pumps	8-9	Technology	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Exploitation of heat/waste heat source for cold production - Integration with thermal RES 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Market availability of some devices - OPEX can be more convenient with respect to vapour compression heat pumps 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Recycling of metal materials - Utilization of spare parts on secondary markets 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - It is mainly linked to the working fluids of the considered absorption heat pump 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Overall positive support 	N.A.
26	Smart Grids	8-9	Technology	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Fundamental for the management of a large number of power injection and consumption points - Management of volatility issues in RES - Support to the electrification of consumption 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Continuous decrease in CAPEX - In many cases Investment profitability is secured by Regulatory Asset Base (RAB) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Recycling of metal materials - Utilization of spare parts on secondary markets 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Positive contribution to environmental impact by allowing a higher penetration of RES in the energy system 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Overall positive support 	N.A.

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27	Energy Communities	N.A.	Strategy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Integration of different demand and supply sources - Better demand and supply balance 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Optimization of the supply cost - Origination of new business opportunities 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Linked to the different technologies integrated in the community 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Reduction of wasted energy - Resource optimization 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Overall positive support 	N.A.
28	OnBill Schemes	N.A.	Strategy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Stimulation to the implementation of energy efficiency measures and RES development - Involvement of energy utilities in the process - Large scale interventions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Attraction of private financing in the renovation and RES market - Development of Energy Efficiency as a service - Implementation of cost-effective measures 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - On bill programs possibly designed to support circularity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Possibility to support measures with a balanced environmental impact 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Perceived as a commercial offer - Free option to consider it or not 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Issues linked to the different income level of males and females existent in some EU countries
29	Green Mortgage	N.A.	Strategy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Support for retrofitting of small properties - Necessity to define clearly the “green projects” - Possibility to set requirements on the EPC level 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Attraction of private capital in the energy efficiency and green markets - Accession to capitals on secondary markets (e.g., from supra-national banks) 	N.A.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Possibility to support only measures with a balanced environmental impact. 	N.A.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Issues linked to the common prejudices existing for usual mortgages when required by minorities
30	On Tax Financing	N.A.	Strategy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Stimulation to the implementation of energy efficiency measures and RES development 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Municipalities take the risk of non-payment - Accession to capitals on secondary markets 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - On tax programs possibly designed to support circularity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Possibility to support measures with a balanced environmental impact 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Possible perception as a support only directed to the upper-middle classes 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Being promoted by public administrations, no gender

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				<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Involvement of municipalities in the process - Targeted interventions according to municipality's needs 	(e.g., from supra-national banks)				issues should be foreseen
31	Demand Flexibility	N.A.	Strategy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Implementation of DSM strategies to adjust the user electricity load on grid requirements - Requires demand side management and optimisation strategies deployed at building level - Schemes for of multiple loads aggregation required - Absence of established regulation and financial schemes limits their deployment - Medium stage development: pilot cases available 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Users' patterns strongly affect the economic turnout - Financial schemes for demand response programmes not yet established 	N.A.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - It can reduce the peak load at network level, thus reducing carbon emissions - DSM programmes leverage on smart algorithms methods, thus optimising the users' energy consumption patterns and related carbon emissions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - It requires smart sensors and network systems to communicate consumption patterns (users' preferences) and system controls - Data protection must be respected - User perceived control on their consumption may be affected, thus reducing the social acceptance of the demand 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Possible issues linked to different energy demand profile due to different general habits between males and females

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								response strategies - Lack of established regulations schemes and contracts may affect the social trust	
32	Virtual Power Plant	N.A.	Strategy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Optimization of RES generation - Reduction of generation volatility - Better management and integration of RES power plants 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - More effective commercial operation of the power plants - Improved trading opportunities - Optimization of the strategic management 	N.A.	N.A.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Positive support due to the high support toward RES - The infrastructure is virtual then there is no local opposition 	N.A.
33	Net Positive Energy District (PED)	N.A.	Strategy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Challenges due to identification of spaces for installation - Adequate climate conditions for the installation of corresponding RES - Management of possible issues linked to grid stabilization 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Extensive investments required - Contribution to the reduction of energy poverty 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Recycling and re-utilization of the technologies included in the PED 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Reduction of carbon and pollutant emissions as a main target - Possible environmental impacts (e.g., visual impact) especially in historical city centres - Land occupation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Positive reaction if created positive value for citizens 	N.A.